

TEACHING ENGLISH MADE ME QUESTION MYSELF: EXPLORING PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS' REFLECTIONS ON EMOTION, CHALLENGES, AND ACTION PLANS

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Abstract: Becoming a teacher is more than learning how to deliver lessons, it also deals about managing emotions, facing unexpected challenges, and constantly reflecting on professional development. This study explores the emotional journeys of ten EFL pre-service teachers during their teaching practice, focusing on how their experiences shaped their reflections and evolving sense of professional identity. Using a Narrative Inquiry approach, the study collected stories through reflecting journals and interviews, capturing both the struggles and insights that emerged throughout the class. Early reflections often revealed feelings of anxiety, self-doubt, and confusion. However, as participants continued reflecting, their narratives became deeper, more honest, and more focused on the progress. Many began to question their initial assumptions about teaching, recognize the role of emotion in the classroom, and build clearer plans for their development. This study offers empirical insights into the interplay between emotion, reflection, and identity, highlighting the importance of supporting pre-service teachers in navigating the emotional complexities of teaching. Implications for teacher education programs include fostering emotionally responsive pedagogies and embedding structured reflective practices to promote holistic professional development.

Keywords: EFL, Narrative Inquiry, Pre-service Teachers, Reflection, Teacher identity

1. INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a dynamic and multifaceted profession that demands continuous learning and adaptation. At the core of this ongoing development lies reflection, a vital skill acknowledged for enhancing teachers' professional growth (Riyanti, 2020). For pre-service teachers, the journey into the profession is particularly transformative, marked by innovative experiences that often challenge preconceived notions of teaching (Catalana, 2020). Despite its recognized importance, many practitioners, especially those still in training, exhibit underdeveloped reflective thinking abilities (Madin & Swanto, 2019). This underscores a critical need for approaches that cultivate deeper, more impactful reflection among aspiring educators.

Pre-service teachers frequently encounter a numerous of challenges during their training, ranging from navigating unfamiliar classroom environments to confronting their own misconceptions about the teaching profession (Catalana, 2020). These practical experiences, such as fieldwork and teaching practicums, serve as rich grounds for learning, yet they can also evoke a wide spectrum of emotions, including uncertainty, frustration, and even feelings of failure (Lutovac & Flores, 2021). The capacity to process these challenging experiences and associated emotions through reflection is fundamental for personal and professional maturation.

Emotion plays an undeniable role in the teaching and learning process, influencing pedagogical decisions and shaping a teacher's overall experience (Richards, 2022). For pre-service teachers, emotions are integral to their developing professional identity and can significantly impact their engagement with reflective practices (Cañabate et al., 2019). Understanding how these emotions meet with the

challenges encountered in real-world teaching scenarios is crucial for fostering genuine self-assessment and facilitating meaningful learning from experience (Murtiana & Risdaneva, 2025).

Reflection itself can manifest in various forms and depths. It is an approach to teacher development that includes reflection on teaching and learning experiences and permits teachers to learn about teaching and learning through example and practice (Widiarti & Rahmah, 2024). Concepts such as reflection-in-action and reflection-on-action are commonly discussed, highlighting the immediate and post-event analysis of teaching practices (Cañabate et al., 2019). While descriptions of experience represent a basic level of reflection, more impactful reflection involves connecting these experiences to theoretical frameworks and critically examining one's own developing pedagogy, moving beyond mere self-concerns to consider impact on students and broader educational implications (Catalana, 2020; Donald & Kahn, 2014). However, studies have noted a scarcity in more thoughtful dialogical and critical reflections among pre-service teachers.

In conducting reflective practice, language teachers can engage in self-reflection, peer reflection, and group reflection (Farrell, 2024). They can use self-reflection to better understand their identity, beliefs, and practices, and how it interacts with the curriculum material (Playsted, 2019). During this reflection process, teachers should be mindful of any personal biases that might influence what they perceive and prefer to perceive. While, teachers can gain a broader perspective by reflecting with peers, whether through a critical friend, team teaching, or peer coaching. These collaborative methods help teachers grow by encouraging reflection, developing skills, and offering mutual support. Language teachers may also reflect with a group of three or more teachers as well as the teachers from similar or different school. When the teachers collaborate in a group, they can cultivate a more collaborative mindset, support one another in expressing their ideas about teaching, and grow professionally as a community.

Engaging in strong reflective practices significantly contributes to the construction of a teacher's professional identity and can positively influence their self-efficacy beliefs (Patterson & Blackmore, 2017). In English as a Foreign Language (EFL) literature classes, student reflections on literary works are a required activity. These reflections serve to capture what students have understood and interpreted from their reading, allowing teachers to assess their responses, determine whether they have grasped the author's intended meaning, and identify any instances of misinterpretation (Adeani et al., 2020). This self-assessment is vital for cultivating the confidence and competence necessary for effective teaching.

Despite the established benefits of reflection, there remains a need to explore in greater depth how pre-service teachers specifically reflect on the emotional dimensions of their teaching challenges and, crucially, how these reflections translate into concrete plans. While some research has investigated how pre-service teachers reflect on their teaching performances generally (Riyanti, 2020), there is less known about the explicit link between their emotional responses to difficulties, their process of questioning themselves, and the subsequent development of strategic plans for improvement and professional development.

This research adopted Gibbs' reflective model (1988) which is widely used for educational purposes (Hashim et al., 2023). This model consists of six stages, involve: Description (what happened?), Feelings (how did you feel?), Evaluation (what was good or bad about the experience?), Analysis (what sense can you make of the situation?), Conclusion (what else could you have done?), and Action plan (what will

you do next time?). One of the key things about Gibbs is the heading of the standing of *Feelings* in reflection. This stage makes it a useful model for some practitioner courses.

Therefore, this article, "Teaching Made Me Question Myself: Exploring Pre-Service Teachers' Reflections on Emotion, Challenges, and Action Plans," aims to investigate the nuanced experiences of pre-service teachers as they navigate the emotional landscape of their training. Specifically, this study explores how pre-service teachers reflect on the challenges they face, the emotions these challenges evoke, and the ways in which these reflections lead to a critical examination of their own practice and the formulation of actionable strategies for future growth. By shedding light on these interconnected aspects, this research seeks to contribute to a more holistic understanding of reflective practice and its role in preparing resilient and adaptable educators.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a **qualitative research design** using **Narrative Inquiry** to explore the lived experiences and emotional reflections of pre-service EFL teachers during their teaching practicum. Narrative Inquiry, as described by **Creswell & Poth (2007)**, is a methodology focused on understanding and representing experiences through the collection and interpretation of personal stories. The focus of this design is not just on what happened, but **how participants interpret their experiences**, particularly their emotional responses, teaching challenges, and how these shape their reflective and developmental processes. The participants of this research are ten pre-service EFL teachers in English Language Education Study Program of UIN Antasari Banjarmasin who completed their teaching practicum.

Data were gathered using two main sources, reflective journals and semi-structure interviews. Participants were asked to write structured reflective journals during their practicum. These journals were guided by **Gibbs' Reflective Cycle (1988)**, which includes six stages: Description, Feelings, Evaluation, Analysis, Conclusion, and Action Plan. This model helped participants articulate not only what happened but how they felt and what they learned.

After the practicum, in-depth interviews were conducted to further explore themes emerging from the journals. The interviews aimed to capture deeper layers of meaning, emotion, and identity development that may not have been fully captured in writing.

The data analysis followed a narrative thematic approach, adapted from the work of Clandinin & Connelly (2000). The steps included:

a. Transcription and Initial Reading

All journal entries and interview transcripts were transcribed and read multiple times to become familiar with the participants' voices.

b. Narrative Coding

Stories were segmented into key episodes (e.g., moments of emotional tension, breakthrough, reflection, and goal-setting).

c. Thematic Analysis

The episodes were analyzed for recurring themes across participants. Particular attention was given to: 1. Emotional expressions (e.g., anxiety, self-

doubt, confidence); 2. Moments of critical reflection and re-evaluation of self; and 3. Evolution of teaching identity and emerging action plans.

d. Story Construction

Participants' experiences were reconstructed into coherent narratives, highlighting their emotional journeys, challenges, and transformation over time.

e. Cross-Case Analysis

Common patterns and divergent experiences across all ten narratives were synthesized to provide a broader picture of pre-service teachers' reflective processes.

In summary, this study employed a Narrative Inquiry approach to explore into the emotional and reflective experiences of ten pre-service EFL teachers during their teaching practicum at UIN Antasari Banjarmasin. By collecting data through structured reflective journals and in-depth interviews, the study captured both surface-level events and deeper personal meanings. Guided by Gibbs' Reflective Cycle and analyzed through a narrative thematic framework, the participants' stories revealed emotional struggles, critical self-reflections, and emerging professional identities. Through careful coding, thematic analysis, and cross-case synthesis, the research provides a comprehensive understanding of how reflective practices contribute to the personal and professional development of future educators.

3. RESULTS

The narratives of the ten pre-service EFL teachers revealed complex emotional and reflective experiences that stretched throughout their teaching practicum. Thematic analysis of their reflective journals and interviews, guided by Gibbs' Reflective Cycle, resulted in three major themes: **(1) Emotional Struggles and Insecurity; (2) Critical Self-Reflections; and (3) Action Planning.**

3.1 Emotional Struggles and Insecurity

At the beginning of their teaching practicum, many participants opened up about feeling emotionally overwhelmed. Their reflections were filled with anxiety, fear, and a strong sense of not being good enough. Some even confessed that they felt like they were just pretending to be teachers, unsure of how to manage the class, plan effective lessons, or respond to students' reactions, as mentioned by PST 1:

“When I was about to start teaching, I felt extremely nervous, especially standing in front of the students. I kept overthinking: "Can I explain the material well?" "Will they understand my teaching?" These thoughts made me dizzy, and I just wanted the lesson to be over quickly. However, I tried to calm myself by taking deep breaths and maintaining my composure because I didn't want my students to see how nervous I was. I feared that if they noticed my anxiety, they might not take me seriously. Despite my efforts, my nervousness persisted, and I struggled to make eye contact with my students during the lesson.”

In her first experience, she felt internal pressure to perform well, such as overthinking with the situation happened. Her statement reveals a deep sense of

insecurity and performance anxiety, which is evident in her persistent self-questioning and overthinking: *"Can I explain the material well?"* and *"Will they understand my teaching?"* These internal dialogues suggest a lack of confidence in her instructional ability, a mark of early-stage teaching identity formation. Her physical reaction *"feeling dizzy and wanting the lesson to be over quickly"* illustrates the **somatic impact of anxiety**, emphasizing that emotional struggles in teaching are not merely mental but can manifest physically, affecting performance and presence in the classroom.

Meanwhile, her difficulty in making eye contact was not just a sign of nervousness, it pointed to something deeper. It showed a sense of distance between her and her students, which can make it harder to connect, communicate, and build a comfortable classroom atmosphere. This hesitation suggested that she had not fully stepped into her role as a teacher yet. Since this experience happened early in her practicum, it highlights just how uncertain and helpless pre-service teachers can feel as they begin their journey into the profession. These experiences illustrate how initial teaching exposure can unsettle the pre-service teachers' confidence and lead to critical questioning of their capabilities.

In line with the statement of PST 1, emotional struggles and insecurity were also faced by PST 3. She felt nervous and unconfident when she spoke in front of the students. She worried of making mistakes in delivering materials so that made the student less of attention. She also felt confused in managing the classroom particularly in handling the situation in the class. Thus, she felt unsuccessful in her first meeting experience, as she said:

"When teaching for the first time, I felt nervous and anxious, especially since I was not accustomed to speaking in front of a class. I worried about making mistakes while delivering the material, which led me to rush through the Simple Present Tense formulas without considering the best way to engage the students. Seeing their lack of interest made me feel disappointed and a little embarrassed, realizing that my approach might not be effective. I also felt confused about how to handle the situation, as this was my first real classroom teaching experience. After finishing the session, I felt relieved but also disheartened that I had not managed to create an engaging lesson."

Another emotional struggle was also happened by PST 4. He switched his feeling from very enthusiastic to less of enthusiastic because of technological constraints, as he stated:

"Before I began teaching, I felt very enthusiastic because I believed that using fables as teaching materials would capture students' attention and make learning more enjoyable. During the lesson, I was excited to present the material, especially seeing my students actively participating and engaging with the content. However, my enthusiasm was dampened by technical difficulties with the projector, which took up valuable class time. Moreover, my poor time management resulted in a rushed and less effective learning

process. Despite these setbacks, I felt somewhat relieved when the lesson ended, even though I knew there were areas I needed to improve for the future.”

The shift from excitement to frustration reveals how **external classroom realities** can emotionally destabilize pre-service teachers. It reflects how **unexpected classroom challenges**, like technology failure, can cause emotional disorder and interrupt the teaching flow. It also points to a gap in **preparedness or contingency planning**, which contributes to the emotional struggle. She fought to fix the technical issue right away, and as time slipped by, so did her initial excitement. What started as a hopeful and energetic lesson quickly turned into a frustrating experience.

Moreover, PST 4 realized that he had not managed the time well, as he said *“my poor time management resulted in a rushed and less effective learning process”*. Instead of blaming the situation, he turned the hidden blame, feeling that his lack of skill was the root of the problem. This moment brought out a deep sense of insecurity and self-doubt. And yet, when the lesson ended, he felt a strange mix of relief and regret—relieved that it was over, but aware that things did not go as planned. Still, in the middle of his emotion, he was aware that this was part of learning. He knew there were things to work on, and that awareness pointed to a growing sense of resilience and a willingness to keep improving.

3.2 Critical Self-Reflections

In this stage, participants moved beyond simply accepting their emotions to critically analyzing the causes and implications of their teaching experiences. Their struggles stemmed not only from external challenges, such as technical issues or student disengagement, but also from gaps in their pedagogical preparation, classroom management strategies, and adaptability.

For some participants, critical reflection began when they realized that even well-prepared activities could fall short if they unnoticed students’ readiness and comfort levels. PST 7, for example, had carefully planned a role-playing activity in which students would practice expressing gratitude, apologizing, and offering sympathy. She expected this to be both meaningful and engaging. However, reality unfolded differently:

“I planned for the students to engage in role-playing exercises where they would practice expressing gratitude for a favor, apologizing for a mistake, and offering sympathy during difficult times. However, as the lesson progressed, I encountered some unexpected challenges. A few students were reluctant to participate in role-playing activities, appearing shy or uncomfortable expressing emotions in front of their peers. This hesitation led to slower engagement than I anticipated.”

Her words mark a turning point in her reflection. She was no longer just telling the story of what happened, but starting to ask herself *why* it happened. Her students’ hesitation made her realize that a good lesson isn’t just about having creative activities on paper; it is also about knowing whether students feel emotionally ready

and culturally comfortable to take part. She began to understand that getting students engaged is not only about their language skills, it is about building trust, easing their anxiety, and making the classroom feel like a safe place to speak up.

The reflection also highlights the importance of **adaptability**. By noting that engagement was slower than expected, the participant is indirectly recognizing the need to adjust strategies in real-time, perhaps by introducing warm-up activities, offering smaller group practice before giving performance, or modeling the role-play more extensively.

Another challenge was dealing with time management. PST 5 admitted that his lesson did not go as smoothly as planned because of issues that could have been anticipated.

“I faced several challenges during the teaching process, such as inadequate preparation of learning media, specifically projectors, which resulted in wasted class time. Additionally, I struggled with time management, which reduced the efficiency of my lesson.”

His reflection shows an important shift from blaming the external factors to acknowledging her role in the situation. He noticed that the delay caused by the projector was not just a technical problem, it was a reminder that being ready to teach also means being ready of using the tools. The few minutes lost at the start disrupted his flow, forcing him to rush through the rest of the lesson and leaving less room for interaction with the students.

He also became aware that his time management needed improvement. It was not only about sticking to the lesson plan, but also about pacing the activities. Thus, the students had enough time to engage, ask questions, and learn the material. This experience made her realize that a great lesson idea can still fall short without good preparation and realistic timing.

In line with challenge of PST 5, PST 9 shared that she had relied on a video to deliver part of her teaching, expecting it to capture students' attention and make the material easier to understand. However, she began to see the gap in her approach as she said:

“I realized that media, such as videos, do not work effectively on their own. They must be supported by strong teaching strategies that maintain students' focus and ensure the material is understandable. Moving forward, I will be more mindful of how I deliver instructions, select appropriate media, and manage my classroom effectively. I also learned that self-evaluation is essential for becoming a better educator.”

She recognized that a video, no matter how interesting, needed to be paired with clear instructions, guided discussion, and strategies that kept students mentally involved. This moment also made her more aware of the importance of classroom management, not as a set of rules, but as a way of keeping the learning process active and focused. Probably, the most telling part of her reflection was her recognition that becoming a better teacher means continually evaluating herself. For her, self-

evaluation was no longer just a post-lesson reflection. It became a mindset, what worked, what didn't, and how she could make for the future lesson better.

3.3 Action Planning

As the final step of Gibbs' reflective model, participants used their insights to set practical goals for future improvement. Dealing with the emotional struggle, PST 10 stated that she will improve her emotional control to be more patient in teaching the students, as she mentioned *"Another area where I need improvement is emotional control, as staying calm under pressure is critical for creating a positive learning environment."* She also planned to attend training events and workshops to gain new perspectives and strategies and to develop more interactive and engaging lesson plans to keep my students motivated and excited about learning.

Meanwhile, PST 5 have a great planning for his teaching later, as she described:

"I am particularly interested in exploring new teaching methods and materials that can make learning more engaging for students. I plan to experiment with different teaching methods and techniques to improve my skills. My goal is to find a teaching style that suits me best so that I can excel in it. I will also continue evaluating methods that I struggle with to enhance my classroom performance."

The participant expressed an interest in experimenting with diverse teaching methods and materials to enhance student engagement, coupled with a commitment to identifying a teaching style that aligns with both personal strengths and classroom effectiveness. By adopted different methods, he can identify the teaching style that not only suits for him personally as a teacher but also it should support student learning. However, he understood that his preferences must be balanced with evidence-based approaches and responsiveness to student feedback.

Dealing with student engagement in using video as learning media, PST 9 have some action plans for reducing the trouble, as she mentioned:

"Before showing videos, I will provide clear instructions and guiding questions to direct students' attention, while ensuring that the videos selected are concise, relevant, and, where possible, interactive. Lessons will begin with attention-grabbing activities, such as discussions or quizzes, and conclude with group discussions or games to reinforce learning. I will strengthen classroom management by addressing distractions immediately and optimizing seating arrangements, while also gathering regular student feedback to evaluate and refine my teaching methods."

The action plan outlines five targeted strategies to address classroom engagement issues, including providing clearer pre-video instructions, selecting shorter and more relevant materials, integrating active learning activities, improving classroom management, and conducting regular learning evaluations. The strategies

align with established best practices in student engagement, such as **active learning, differentiated instruction, and formative assessment.**

Furthermore, PST 8 suggested the similar action plans that she will conduct in the future if she faced the problem of teaching materials as the following:

“In the future, I can be better prepared by keeping backup materials on a flash drive or another device. This would ensure that I have access to the necessary resources even if my primary device fails. Additionally, I have learned the importance of having a backup plan and remaining calm in emergency situations. Flexibility and creativity are crucial in teaching, and I will make it a priority to check the equipment thoroughly before class starts to prevent similar issues.”

The participant’s action plan shows a practical and thoughtful approach to avoid technical difficulties in the classroom. By keeping backup materials on another device, checking equipment before class, and staying flexible and creative, she prepares to handle unexpected problems with confidence. This reflection suggested to stay calm and adapt during emergencies. While the plan is hard in terms of prevention, it could be even stronger by including non-digital backup options to keep lessons running smoothly, even without technology.

4. DISCUSSION

The findings from this study reveal a connection between pre-service teachers’ reflections, self-awareness, and professional development as an EFL teachers. Early experiences were often marked by anxiety, self-doubt, and uncertainty, reflecting the less of confidence of pre service teachers at the first time they came into real classrooms. This aligns with Lutovac and Flores (2021), who note that initial teaching encounters can disturb professional identity formation, prompting critical self-questioning.

In the beginning of their teaching practicums, participants frequently experienced emotional struggles like anxiety and insecurity. These emotions were not just mental but also demonstrated physically, affecting their classroom performance and presence. For example, one participant's nervousness led to difficulty making eye contact with students, which created a sense of distance. Another participant's enthusiasm was dampened by technical problems, leading to frustration and a rushed lesson. These emotional reactions, in line with previous research, show that a teacher's professional identity is deeply influenced by their emotional responses to real-world teaching situations (Murtiana & Risdaneva, 2025).

Instead of accusing external factors, the pre service teachers began to question their own assumptions and pedagogical approaches. One participant realized that a well-planned activity was not enough if the students were not emotionally ready to participate, which highlights the importance of adapting to the classroom context. This shift from attributing problems to external factors toward recognizing one’s own responsibility marks an important indicator of emerging reflective thinking and advancing professional development. In this way, the

reflective process became not just a means of processing emotions but a tool for continuous improvement, empowering participants to make informed, intentional adjustments to their teaching (Catalana, 2020).

The action plans created by participants show a clear progress in both confidence and adaptability. These plans cover a range of strategies from improving lesson planning and integrating media more effectively to strengthening emotional control and preparing for unexpected situations. Together, they reflect their commitment to evidence-based, student-centered teaching. The focus on flexibility, preparation, and gathering feedback suggests that participants are developing the kind of reflective resilience (Farrell, 2024) for a sustainable teaching career. Moreover, many of the plans relied heavily on technical prevention measures, with less attention to low-tech or pedagogical alternatives, pointing to a need for further guidance in expanding their problem-solving approaches.

Another participant who faced technical difficulties and poor time management created an action plan that included having backup materials on a flash drive and checking equipment before class. This demonstrates a move from feeling helpless in a difficult situation to proactively preparing to prevent similar issues in the future. Similarly, the participant who realized a video alone was not an effective teaching tool planned to incorporate clearer instructions, guiding questions, and follow-up activities to reinforce learning. These action plans illustrate the transformative power of reflection. It allows pre-service teachers to turn moments of uncertainty into clear, strategic steps for professional development. This is a clear indicator that their reflective process moved beyond mere self-concerns to consider their impact on students and broader educational implications.

5. CONCLUSION

This study highlights that becoming a teacher is a journey of involving managing emotions, confronting unexpected challenges, and constantly reflecting on teachers' professional development. The emotional struggles and insecurities experienced by pre-service teachers, though difficult, are not just complications, they are vital opportunities for evolution when approached through structured reflection. The narratives of the ten participants clearly show that by reflecting deeply on their emotions and challenges, they were able to critically examine their practices and develop actionable plans for improvement.

The findings have significant implications for teacher education programs. By embedding structured reflective practices, such as the use of Gibbs' Reflective Cycle, programs can better prepare aspiring educators for the emotional complexities of teaching. Fostering an environment that encourages honest, critical self-assessment, moving beyond surface-level reflections to more impactful ones, can help pre-service teachers cultivate the self-awareness, resilience, and adaptability necessary for a successful and fulfilling career. Ultimately, this research highlights that pre service teachers journey is not just about what they teach, but also about what they learn about themselves and their own practice along the way.

REFERENCES

- Adeani, I. S., Febriani, R. B., & Syafryadin. (2020). Using GIBBS' reflective cycle in making reflections of literary analysis. *Indonesian EFL Journal*, 6(2), 139-148. <https://doi.org/10.25134/ieflij.v6i2.3382>
- Cañabate, D., Serra, T., Bubnys, R., & Colomer, J. (2019). Pre-service teachers' reflections on cooperative learning: Instructional approaches and identity construction. *Sustainability*, 11(21), 5970. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11215970>
- Catalana, S. M. (2020). Indicators of impactful reflection in pre-service teachers: A case for creativity, honesty and unfamiliar experiences. *International Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, 14(1), 14. <https://doi.org/10.20429/ijstl.2020.140114>
- Clandinin, D. J., & Connelly, F. M. (2000). *Narrative inquiry: Experience and story in qualitative research*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2007). *Qualitative Inquiry & Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches* (Second, Vol. 2, Issue June). Sage Publications. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Rulinawaty-Kasmad/publication/342229325_Second_Edition_QUALITATIVE_INQUIRY_RESEARCH_DESIGN_Choosing_Among_Five_Approaches/links/5eec7025458515814a6ac263/Second-Edition-QUALITATIVE-INQUIRY-RESEARCH-DESIGN-Choosing-Among
- Farell, T. S. (2024). *Reflective Parctice for Language Teachers*. British council.
- Gibbs, G. (1988). *Learning by doing: A guide to teaching and learning methods*. Oxford: Oxford Further Education Unit.
- Hashim, S. N. A., Yaacob, A., Suryani, I., Asraf, R. M., Bahador, Z., & Supian, N. (2023). Exploring the Use of Gibbs' Reflective Model in Enhancing In-Service ESL Teachers' Reflective Writing. *Arab World English Journal*, 14(2). <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol14no2.17>
- Lutovac, S., & Assuncao Flores, M. (2021). 'Those who fail should not be teachers': Pre-service Teachers' Understandings of Failure and Teacher Identity Development. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 47(3), 379-394. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2021.1891833>
- McDonald, D., & Kahn, M. (2014). " So, You Think You Can Teach?"-Reflection Processes That Support Pre-Service Teachers' Readiness for Field Experiences. *International Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, 8(2), n2. <https://doi.org/10.20429/ijstl.2014.080218>
- Murtiana, R. (2025). " I feel unappreciated because I'm not the real teacher": Understanding pre-service teachers' emotions and identity. *Journal of English and Education (JEE)*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.20885/jee.v11i1.39636>

- Playsted, S. A. (2019). Reflective Practice to Guide Teacher Learning: A Practitioner's Journey with Beginner Adult English Language Learners. *Iranian Journal of Language Teaching Research*, 7(3), 37-52.
- Richards, J. C. (2022). Exploring emotions in language teaching. *relc Journal*, 53(1), 225-239. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0033688220927531>
- Riyanti, D. (2020). Students' reflections in teaching practicum: A case study of EFL pre-service teachers. *Journal on English as a Foreign Language*, 10(2), 268-289. <https://doi.org/10.23971/jefl.v10i2.2041>
- Patterson, K., & Seabrooks-blackmore, J. J. (2017). The effects of self-reflection and classroom management course on pre-service teachers' self-efficacy. *Journal of Theoretical Educational Science*, 10(3), 335-348. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5578/keg.57464>
- Val Madin, C., & Swanto, S. (2019). An Inquiry Approach to Facilitate Reflection in Action Research for ESL Pre-Service Teachers. *TEFLIN Journal: A Publication on the Teaching & Learning of English*, 30(1). <http://dx.doi.org/10.15639/teflinjournal.v30i1/1-21>
- Widiastari, N., & Fithriani, R. (2024). Teachers' Practices of Reflective Teaching in EFL Classroom. *IJORER: International Journal of Recent Educational Research*, 5(3), 679-689. <https://doi.org/10.46245/ijorer.v5i3.591>